

NEW REALIZATIONS OF SECOND-ORDER ALL-PASS TRANSFER FUNCTIONS

Ana D. Simić and Miroslav D. Lutovac

IRITEL Institute, Batajnički put 23,

11080 Belgrade, Yugoslavia,

ana@iritel.bg.ac.yu lutovac@iritel.bg.ac.yu

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an implementation of a systematic method for realization of the second-order all-pass transfer functions using the minimum number of multipliers. The presented realizations are analyzed with regard to the error due to roundoff of the products. The realizations are compared in order to determine optimum realization for particular pole position. Using these filter sections for realisation of some recursive transfer function as the parallel connection of two all-pass networks, will lead us to the computationally efficient realization with low pass-band sensitivity.

1 INTRODUCTION

An important class of digital transfer functions is all-pass transfer function defined by:

$$G(z) = \frac{z^{-m} + a_{m-1}z^{-m+1} + \dots + a_1z^{-1} + a_0}{1 + a_{m-1}z^{-1} + \dots + a_1z^{-m+1} + a_0z^{-m}}. \quad (1)$$

It is widely used for the realization of pulse compression filters, phase equalizers, etc [1]. Also, certain class of digital filter transfer function can be realized as a parallel connection of two all-pass filters, leading to a implementations characterised by low pass-band sensitivity and which are computationally efficient [2]. Those all-pass filters can be realized using any of the general realization methods, or with regard to some characteristic of the special interest. In this paper we consider that all-pass functions are realized as a cascade of first-order and second-order sections

$$G(z) = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{z^{-2} + a_{i1}z^{-1} + a_{i0}}{1 + a_{i1}z^{-1} + a_{i0}z^{-2}} \prod_{r=1}^{m-2n} \frac{z^{-1} + b_{r0}}{1 + b_{r0}z^{-m}}. \quad (2)$$

This paper presents the method used for synthesis of new realizations of all-pass digital filter using a minimum number of multipliers.

The systematic method for realization is proposed in [1] and implemented on two different forms of the transfer function of second order and on one first order function, as well. Here, the proposed procedure is applied

on another form of second-order all-pass transfer function and all possible realizations are presented. Some of realizations are published earlier, but few realizations with very low pass-band sensitivity are new.

The results are derived in systematic form (transfer matrix) which is convenient for analysis or for the classification by some parameter of interest. Further more, the derived realizations are analyzed by calculating the roundoff error in order to find the optimum solution for a particular pole position.

2 PROPOSED METHOD

A systematic method for realization of an all-pass digital transfer function using a minimum number of multipliers is given in [1]. The method is based on the multiplier extraction approach. The transfer functions are realized in a form of a cascade of the first-order and the second-order all-pass sections, as in (2). The method is, in [1], applied on the first-order section and on the second-order section and will be here explained on the example of the second-order section. The parameters b_2 and b_3 are assumed to be real and they represent the multiplier coefficients, two of them for the second-order transfer function.

The realization of filter section is considered as a constrained three-pair, as given in Figure 1, where three-pair N contains only delays and adders.

Figure 1: A constrained three-pair

The network of Figure 1 is characterized by following

system of equations:

$$\begin{bmatrix} Y_1 \\ Y_2 \\ Y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} t_{11} & t_{12} & t_{13} \\ t_{21} & t_{22} & t_{23} \\ t_{31} & t_{32} & t_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_1 \\ X_2 \\ X_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$X_2 = b_2 Y_2 \quad (4)$$

$$X_3 = -b_3 Y_3. \quad (5)$$

where t_{ij} are the transfer parameters of the three pair N. Solving equations (3)-(5), we obtain expression for the transfer function:

$$\frac{Y_1}{X_1} = t_{11} + [b_2 t_{12} - b_3 t_{13}] \begin{bmatrix} 1 - b_2 t_{22} & b_3 t_{23} \\ -b_2 t_{32} & 1 + b_3 t_{33} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} t_{21} \\ t_{31} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

Comparing the denominator and denominator of particular form of transfer function with one of (6), we obtain seven equations leading to a set of possible values for t_{ij} . Every transfer matrix, obtained that way, corresponds to a different realization of transfer function.

Different realizations have different performances in practice due to parameter quantization. We assume the fixed point implementation, where each signal is represented by B bits (plus a sign bit). The quantization of products on the outputs of each multiplier imposes an error in system which limits the number of bits actually useful for the presentation of the multiplier coefficients, so it is useful to evaluate that error. The error on the output of the multiplier b_i can be considered as a set of noise samples $E_{b_i}(nT)$, superimposed on the signal $X_i(nT)$. The noise model is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The noise model

The variance of the $E_{b_i}(nT)$ is $\frac{q^2}{12}$, assuming that the noise samples are uniformly distributed within quantization interval q . The corresponding noise variance at the output of the filter is given by:

$$\sigma_i^2 = \frac{q^2}{12(2\pi j)} \oint H_i(z) H_i(z^{-1}) z^{-1} dz \quad (7)$$

where $H_i(z)$ is the transfer function from the output of the multiplier b_i to the filter output. The overall noise variance σ^2 is given by the sum of all noise variances.

Functions $H_i(z)$ can be easily derived using the transfer parameters of the three-pair N, and are given by:

$$H_2(z) = \frac{t_{12} + b_3(t_{12}t_{33} - t_{13}t_{32})}{1 - b_2t_{22} + b_3t_{33} - b_2b_3(t_{22}t_{33} - t_{23}t_{32})} \quad (8)$$

$$H_3(z) = \frac{t_{13} - b_2(t_{13}t_{22} - t_{12}t_{23})}{1 - b_2t_{22} + b_3t_{33} - b_2b_3(t_{22}t_{33} - t_{23}t_{32})}. \quad (9)$$

Solving equation (7) using $H_i(z)$ given by (8) and (9), lead us to the expression for the value of the output noise variance as a function of pole radius and angle.

3 IMPLEMENTATION OF ALGORITHM

The proposed method is systematic and it can be easily described by an algorithm, so it is convenient for implementation in software [3].

The method is applied on the another form of an all-pass transfer function:

$$G_3(z) = \frac{z^{-2} - b_2(1 + b_3)z^{-1} + b_3}{1 - b_2(1 + b_3)z^{-1} + b_3z^{-2}}. \quad (10)$$

The form given by (10) is proposed in [4] and some of possible realizations are also presented in [4]. The goal was to derive all possible realizations of all-pass transfer function given by (10). Choosing the form (10) as an input, we arrive at following system of equations:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} t_{22} = z^{-1} \\ t_{33} = z^{-2} \\ t_{11} = z^{-2} \\ t_{23}t_{32} = z^{-3} - z^{-1} \\ t_{12}t_{21} = z^{-3} - z^{-1} \\ t_{13}t_{31} = z^{-4} - 1 \\ t_{21}t_{13}t_{32} + t_{31}t_{12}t_{23} = 2z^{-3}(z^{-2} - 1). \end{array} \right. \quad (11)$$

Solving the system (11) we derive the set of 18 different transfer matrixes, each representing different realization and 18 corresponding transposes (Table1).

4 ROUND OFF ERROR

Further more, analytical expressions for the output noise variance for each of these realizations have been derived. It could be noticed that there are 18 pairs of realizations leading to 18 different expressions for roundoff noise variance.

On Figure 3, the curves representing some of the realizations for the pole radius 0.25 are plotted for pole angle in interval $0^\circ \div 180^\circ$. The realization marked A (Figure 4) is shown to be the best for small pole radii. In practice it is usually more effective to use realization

$A = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & 1 & 1 \\ z^{-1}(z^{-2}-1) & z^{-1} & z^{-1} \\ z^{-4}-1 & z^{-2}-1 & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$	$B = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & 1 & z^{-1}+1 \\ z^{-1}(z^{-2}-1) & z^{-1} & z^{-1}(z^{-1}+1) \\ (z^{-2}+1)(z^{-1}+1) & z^{-1}-1 & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$
$C = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & 1 & z^{-1}-1 \\ z^{-1}(z^{-2}-1) & z^{-1} & z^{-1}(z^{-1}-1) \\ (z^{-2}+1)(z^{-1}+1) & z^{-1}+1 & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$	$D = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & 1 & z^{-2}-1 \\ z^{-1}(z^{-2}-1) & z^{-1} & z^{-1}(z^{-2}-1) \\ z^{-2}-1 & 1 & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$
$E = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & 1 & z^{-2}+1 \\ z^{-1}(z^{-2}-1) & z^{-1} & z^{-1}(z^{-2}-1) \\ z^{-2}-1 & 1 & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$	$F = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & z^{-1} & 1 \\ z^{-2}-1 & z^{-1} & 1 \\ z^{-4}-1 & z^{-1}(z^{-1}-1) & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$
$G = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & z^{-1} & z^{-1}+1 \\ z^{-2}-1 & z^{-1} & z^{-1}+1 \\ (z^{-2}+1)(z^{-1}-1) & z^{-1}(z^{-1}-1) & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$	$H = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & z^{-1} & z^{-1}-1 \\ z^{-2}-1 & z^{-1} & z^{-1}-1 \\ (z^{-1}+1)(z^{-2}+1) & z^{-1}(z^{-1}+1) & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$
$I = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & z^{-1} & z^{-2}-1 \\ z^{-2}-1 & z^{-1} & z^{-2}-1 \\ z^{-2}+1 & z^{-1} & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$	$J = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & z^{-1} & z^{-2}+1 \\ z^{-2}-1 & z^{-1} & z^{-2}-1 \\ z^{-2}-1 & z^{-1} & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$
$K = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & z^{-1}+1 & z^{-1}+1 \\ z^{-1}(z^{-1}-1) & z^{-1} & z^{-1} \\ (z^{-2}+1)(z^{-1}-1) & z^{-2}-1 & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$	$L = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & z^{-1}+1 & z^{-2}-1 \\ z^{-1}(z^{-1}-1) & z^{-1} & z^{-1}(z^{-1}-1) \\ z^{-2}+1 & z^{-1}+1 & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$
$M = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & z^{-1}+1 & z^{-2}+1 \\ z^{-1}(z^{-1}-1) & z^{-1} & z^{-1}(z^{-1}-1) \\ z^{-2}-1 & z^{-1}+1 & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$	$N = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & z^{-1}+1 & (z^{-2}+1)(z^{-1}+1) \\ z^{-1}(z^{-1}-1) & z^{-1} & z^{-1}(z^{-2}-1) \\ z^{-1}-1 & 1 & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$
$O = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & z^{-1}-1 & z^{-1}-1 \\ z^{-1}(z^{-1}+1) & z^{-1} & z^{-1} \\ (z^{-2}+1)(z^{-1}+1) & z^{-2}-1 & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$	$P = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & z^{-1}-1 & z^{-2}-1 \\ z^{-1}(z^{-1}+1) & z^{-1} & z^{-1}(z^{-1}+1) \\ z^{-2}+1 & z^{-1}-1 & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$
$Q = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & z^{-1}-1 & z^{-2}+1 \\ z^{-1}(z^{-1}+1) & z^{-1} & z^{-1}(z^{-1}+1) \\ z^{-2}-1 & z^{-1}-1 & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$	$R = \begin{bmatrix} z^{-2} & z^{-1}-1 & (z^{-2}+1)(z^{-1}-1) \\ z^{-1}(z^{-1}+1) & z^{-1} & z^{-1}(z^{-2}-1) \\ z^{-1}+1 & 1 & z^{-2} \end{bmatrix}$

Table 1: Transfer matrixes

marked J (Figure 5) because it uses two, instead four delay elements and it is second best in wide range of pole angles.

Usually, more important is the behavior of noise gain functions for large pole radii. The curves representing noise gain functions for pole radius 0.75 are plotted in Figure 6. From that figure, we can observe that realizations marked J, M (Figure 7) and Q (Figure 8) are the best in particular intervals of pole angle. Actually, the same conclusion is valid for large interval of pole radii, starting from near 0.5, to the higher values of pole radius approaching unity.

5 CONCLUSION

The systematic method for realization of a second-order all-pass transfer function is applied, leading to new realizations. Those realizations are compared with regard to error generated due to the round-off of multiplication products. The variance of the error is computed and presented as a function of pole angle and radius. Using results of that analysis, it is possible to find optimum realization for particular pole position having minimal roundoff error.

References

- [1] Mitra, S.K., Hirano, K., "Digital All-Pass Networks," IEEE Transactions on Circuit and Systems, pp.688-700, September 1974.
- [2] Vaidyanathan, P. P., Mitra, S. K., Neuvo, Y., "A New Approach to the Realization of Low-Sensitivity IIR Digital Filters," IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing, Vol. ASSP-34, No2, pp. 350-361, April 1986.
- [3] Simic, A., Lutovac, M., "Symbolic Synthesis of All-Pass Transfer Functions," Proceedings of DSP97, Vol.2, pp. 463-466, Santorini, Greece, July 1997.
- [4] Ansari, R., Lui, B., "A Class of Low-Noise Computationally Efficient Recursive Digital Filters with Applications to Sampling Rate Alterations," IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing, Vol. ASSP-33, No1, pp. 90-97, February 1985.

Figure 3: Noise variance for $r=0.25$

Figure 6: Noise variance for $r=0.75$

Figure 4: Realization marked A

Figure 7: Realization marked M

Figure 5: Realization marked J

Figure 8: Realization marked Q